

THEORETICAL AND EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF VISCOUS TORSIONAL DAMPER ON TURBOCHARGED INLINE SIX CYLINDER ENGINE

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ABSTRACT:

The torsional vibration of diesel engines is severe issue due to increase of exciting force by higher pressure in turbocharged heavy duty engines. Diesel Engine crankshaft experiences the torsional vibration excitation torque due to the effect of cylinder firing pressure and the inertia of the reciprocating parts. These large torsional vibration amplitudes can cause noise, bearing wear, crankshaft failure. In order to attenuate the too large value of resonant torsional vibration amplitude the viscous damper is mounted on crankshaft crank nose end. The current work focus on experimentation torsional vibration damper for inline six cylinder turbocharged diesel engine for limiting the crank nose end torsional vibration amplitude within specified limit for entire speed range. For designing the damper multi mass system converted into lumped mass system. The natural frequency and torsional vibration amplitude is determined by Holzer tabulation method and also by using engine simulation software. For simulation purpose, various prototypes with varying viscosity, inertia & internal clearance. The prototypes was considered.. The engine torsional vibration (TV) analysis is carried out for different prototype samples considered and results are compared with bare crankshaft torsional vibration amplitude. Experimental results will be compared with the theoretical results generated by engine simulation software.

KEYWORDS: Torsional vibration, Natural frequency, Torsional vibration amplitude, Torsional vibration analyzer, Holzer method. Engine simulation. Phase vector summation.

LITERATURE REVIEW:

- [1] **Kodama, T. Katsuhiko Wakabayashi and Yasuhiro Honda** have performed experiment to determine the dynamic characteristics of the viscous friction damper by the method by adopting simultaneous vibration measurement method at two points. The experiment, the vibration displacements of the damper casing and the inertia ring can be simultaneously measured in this method he concluded the dynamic properties of the silicone fluid can be obtained by changing the clearances between the viscosities of fluid. The torsional vibration amplitudes at damper casing and the Inertia ring are calculated by using the pulse tapes & acrylic casing. Damper optimum internal clearance are decided by experimentation
- [2] **E.J Nestorides** gives the number of formulae for the crankshaft stiffness calculation for variety of configurations of crankshaft. The various damper design criteria's for moment of inertia of seismic mass, m.i of casing and surface area for heat dissipation are proposed.
- [3] **Wilson, W.K [volm two]** has proposed the methods for calculation of the natural frequency of rotating multi mass system. This also gives the phase angle diagram and phase angle vector summation for various configurations of the engines.
- [4] **WojciechHomik** has described the causes of torsional vibrations in the engine crankshaft. also proposed the method for damper design for specific application. also proposed that the maximum working

temperature of viscous damper is 120 degree C. But the seizing of the viscous damper will happen when the damper surface temperature exceed by 60 deg. C from damper design temperature.

[5] **Mark A. Carbo and Stanley B. Malanoski** has proposed the method for encounter the torsional vibration difficulties in practical. He had proposed the method for obtaining the natural frequency in practical case also mentioned steps to be taken once the natural frequencies are calculated to avoid the resonance condition also The Torsional vibration problem associated with the start up motor is discussed.

[6] **Meirelles, P.S. et al.** "Mathematical Model for Torsional Vibration Analysis in Internal Combustion Engines", 12th IFToMM World Congress, Besançon (France), June 18 – 21, 2007.

The scope of this paper is the study of the crankshaft torsional vibration phenomenon in internal combustion engines. The formulation, based on state equation solution with system steady state response calculation performed by transition state matrix and the convolution integral. The analysis considers a rubber and a viscous damper assembled to the crankshaft front-end. From the torsional vibrations analysis, it is possible to obtain the dynamic loading on each crankshaft section and these loads can be applied as boundary conditions in a finite element model to predict the safety factor of the component and compare the system behavior with rubber and viscous damping options. By this way, it is possible to emphasize the importance of the torsional vibrations analysis on the structural dimensioning of the crankshafts.

[7] **Torsional Vibration, Cummins Engineering Standards – 98087.** The standard explains about various types of damper and theory related to working of torsional vibration damper. It also explains the formulae for calculating the heat generation and heat dissipation and the standard method of testing for engines.

[8] **D. E. Zampieri, A. S. Mendes, P. S. Meirelles,** "Experimental Validation of Methodology for Torsional Vibration Analysis in Internal Combustion Engines." 12th IFToMM World Congress Besancon (France), June 18-21, 2007.

The scope of this paper is the study of the crankshaft torsional vibration phenomenon in internal combustion engines. The formulation, based on state equation solution with system steady state response calculation done by transition state matrix and the convolution integral, will be applied to a six-cylinder Diesel engine for vehicular application manufactured by MWM International Motores. The analysis considers a rubber and a viscous damper assembled to the crankshaft front-end. From the torsional vibrations analysis, it is possible to obtain the dynamic loading on each crankshaft section and these loads can be applied as boundary conditions in a finite element model to predict the safety factor of the component and compare the system behavior with rubber and viscous damping options. By this way, it is possible to emphasize the importance of the torsional vibrations analysis on the structural dimensioning of the crankshafts. The vibration amplitudes results will be compared to measured values for experimental validation of proposed mathematical model.

[9] **P.S. Meirelles, D.E. Zampieri, A.S. Mendes,** Authors has proposed the formulation for torsional vibration analysis of six cylinder diesel engine for vehicular engine. Analysis includes the comparison of results of engine by using the rubber and viscous damper. Vibration amplitude results compared with measured values for experimental validation.

[10] **Jouji Kimura, Ryoji Kai,** Author has performed the torsional vibration analysis of the on six cylinder in-line engine turbo-charged diesel engine crankshaft. It has observed that, in case of turbo charged engine significant degree of a low harmonic order exciting torque acts on the crankshaft. The 3rd order non resonant amplitude is not only significant but also characteristics of the turbocharged engine in comparison with naturally aspirated engine.

[11] **Homik W** Author presented the causes of various types vibrations in multi cylinder engine, particular attention was on torsional vibration which is severe threat to engine crankshaft. Also presented damping

method, problems of damping efficiency, change of viscosity, amplitude-frequency characteristics of various viscous dampers

[12] WLADYSLAW MITIANIEC, KONRAD BUCZEK "Torsional Vibration Analysis of Crankshaft in Heavy Duty Six Cylinder Inline Engine" ISBN 001-4561, ISBN 01897-6328. In paper author studied torsional vibration analysis of crankshaft in six cylinder inline heavy duty engine taking advantage of the crank train reduction to multi mass model. The Results of multi mass model compared with FEM results. The error between two methods is not significant hence the multi mass model reflects the reality.

[13] Tray Feese & Charles Hill "Guidelines for preventing Torsional vibration problems in reciprocating machinery". The purpose of this course is to raise awareness of torsional vibration problem that can occur in reciprocating equipment, and to give guidelines based on experience with accurate systems to avoid these problems in future while designing any torsional system. A list of recommended items that should be considered in the initial design stage, analysis stage, and after the system is in service provided to help attain maximum reliability. The need for torsional vibration measurements during commissioning to verify acceptability of critical applications is also discussed.

In this paper different case histories are presented where failure were linked to torsional vibration. In general, the solutions to these problems were based on practical considerations that could be retrofitted in the field. Of particular interest are the failures that could not have been predicted if only an "ideal" operating condition was analyzed. The results of these investigations emphasize the need for more comprehensive torsional analysis in the design stage of critical systems.

[14] Wang Mengsheng, Zhou Ruiping and Xu Xiang "The Engine Silicone-oil Damper Matching Calculation Method Based on the Heat Balance." ISSN: 2040-7467. The author studied the heat balance of silicone type damper by analyzing the internal relations with the silicone-oil damper conditions, the temperature, the viscosity of silicone-oil and the dynamic equilibrium established in the study process. The silicone-oil damper matching calculation method is proposed based on the heat balance established, to prove the validity of the calculation method for the accurately matching calculation and designing method.

INTRODUCTION:

Torsional vibration is one prominent issue in case of multi cylinder engines. The engine is subjected to the torsional vibration problem due to gas pressure and reciprocating inertia forces in the multi cylinder engine. The all the rotating and reciprocating machines are subjected to great concern of the torsional vibration. The engines are designed for high load condition with increased power density. This increase power in turbocharged engine leads to serious torsional vibration problem for crankshaft. This excessive amplitude of the torsional vibration results into noise, wear, reduced reliability and service life of engine, excessive stresses or even fatigue failure of crankshaft. To reduce such excessive torsional vibration amplitude and avoid resonant conditions torsional vibration dampers are introduced in crankshaft assembly. The friction type silicone fluid viscous vibration with is mostly used to attenuate the torsional vibrations in multi-cylinder heavy duty engine applications, The experimental analysis of torsional vibration characteristics are carried out with the different torsional damper proto samples on diesel test engine.

For significant torsional vibration to occur, three conditions shall be met-

- i) The exciting frequency of engines one of the order should match the natural frequency of the shaft system.
- ii) The exciting order has large amplitude.
- iii) The result of phase vector summation is large.

The torsional vibration dampers are classified as rubber and viscous dampers based on the coupling media used between the hub and the inertia ring.

A) RUBBER DAMPER:

Crankshaft rubber damper is an example of a damped, tuned absorber. The damper is composed of an inertia ring, a rubber element, and a hub as shown in fig1. The inertia ring is connected to the hub through the rubber element. Due to shear of rubber element heat is generated inside the rubber.

Fig no 1. Schematic of rubber damper

The rubber dampers are “tuned “damper, since they are tuned to specific frequency of engine crankshaft. The rubber damper will split the crankshaft resonance into two modes, one on higher side & second on lower side of the critical mode peak and add damping to attenuate the amplitude of the torsional vibration as shown in the following figure no.2.it is the most weight-efficient design. It has its entire supporting hub on the inside and the entire working inertia ring on the outside

Fig no. 2 Working principle of rubber damper

B) VISCOUS DAMPERS:

The inertia ring is completely enclosed in the housing and surrounded with a very thin layer of high viscosity fluid see below fig. 3. The peripheral and lateral gaps between these two members are filled with a viscous fluid with high viscosity e.g. silicone fluid. The damper is ‘untuned’, since there is no elastic coupling member between the seismic mass and the casing; the seismic mass is acted upon only by the viscous torque transmitted by the fluid.

Fig no.3. Schematic of viscous damper

Unlike ‘tuned’ dampers, the untuned viscous shear damper does not introduce an additional resonance, but lowers the value of vibration amplitudes at the natural frequency due to damping of silicon fluid as shown in fig.4.

Fig no.4. Working principle of viscous damper

The inertia ring is free to rotate (back and forth), and it too lags the crank Torsional motion and applies a lagging torque to the crank nose. The ring motion running back and forth in the housing shears the fluid and the fluid absorbs energy. They are the best choice for truck and marine diesels.

THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN TORSIONAL VIBRATION ANALYSIS:

The torsional vibration analysis is necessary for multimass system to avoid the resonance and failure of shaft. to avoid failure of machine from application detailed analysis is required. Torsional Vibration Analysis [TVA] in detail would comprise of following steps:

- Determination of torsional natural frequencies
- Determination of torsional mode shapes
- Development of interference margin analysis
- Determination of coincidences of the harmonics of excitation frequencies with the torsional natural frequencies and the corresponding operating speeds of the engine.
- Calculation of steady state torsional amplitudes of all the rotors based on torque modulations and magnification factors.
- Engine order analysis in order to determine major critical orders and minor critical orders
- Engine harmonic analysis
- Determination of Vector summations
- Determination of Torsional stresses in all the shafts considering torque modulations and magnification factors
- Comparison of results with applicable standard codes or standard norms specified by various classification societies.

INPUTS REQUIRED FOR DESIGN OF VISCOUS DAMPER:

The inputs required for TVA are as follows:

- Mass elastic model and data:
- Number of cylinders.
- Rated speed of engine.
- Main journal diameter.
- Crank pin diameter.
- Cylinder bore diameter.
- Single cylinder forcing data function
- Packaging space.

SPECIFICATIONS OF TEST ENGINE :(CASE STUDY)

The test engine used for the measurement of torsional vibration angular displacement is the 6 cylinders, Inline, automotive diesel engine .The specification of the test engine are given in table 1as below:

Table 1: Specifications of Experimental Test Engine

Perticulars	Contents
Designed for	Diesel engine -
Type	4-Stroke Cycle, Direct
No. of Cylinders	6-Cylinders
Arrangement	In-line
Bore and stroke (m)	0.110x0.145 m
Max. Brake power output Kw/rpm	210/2200
Low Idle /High Idle speed (rpm)	600/2750
Firing Order	1-5-3-6-2-4

LUMPED MASS MODEL OF ENGINE:

Fig 5. Lumped mass Crankshaft model for 6-cylinder inline Engine.

The standard procedure calculations the moments of inertia is to concentrate the each crank throw, including the connecting rod and piston, at the corresponding cylinder center position on the equivalent shaft representing the crankshaft.

The polar moment of inertia and torsional stiffness between two cylinder are calculated and tabulated as below

MOMENT OF INERTIA CALCULATION:

The polar moment of inertia and torsional stiffness between two cylinder are calculated and tabulated as below

Table 2: moment of Inertia & torsional Stiffness of crankshaft table

S.N	Mass Station	M.I(Kg-m ²)	Stiffness (MNm/rad)
1	Pulley+Hub	0.09	6.545
2	FGT	0.0025	2.338
3	Crankthrow 1	0.039	1.203
4	Crankthrow 2	0.38	1.203
5	Crankthrow 3	0.038	1.356
6	Crankthrow 4	0.038	1.40
7	Crankthrow 5	0.038	1.203
8	Crankthrow 6	0.039	2.463
9	RGT	0.026	4.3
10	Flywheel	0.611	

This generated mass elastic data used for torsional vibration analysis.

NATURAL FREQUENCY CALCULATION –HOLZER METHOD:

The first step in any torsional analysis procedure is determination of the system's natural frequencies and mode shapes. The lumped parameter model is developed for disk and shaft elements, in which the discs represent the system's inertial components while the shaft element of torsional system behaves as torsional springs. System converted into 3 equivalent mass system. The first two approximate natural frequencies are obtained by

$$\omega_1^2, \omega_2^2 = 1/2 \left[\left(\frac{Kt_1}{J_1} + \frac{Kt_1 + Kt_2}{J_2} + \frac{Kt_2}{J_3} \right) \mp \sqrt{\left(\frac{Kt_1}{J_1} + \frac{Kt_1 + Kt_2}{J_2} + \frac{Kt_2}{J_3} \right)^2 - (4 \cdot Kt_1 \cdot Kt_2 \cdot \frac{J_1 + J_2 + J_3}{J_1 \cdot J_2 \cdot J_3})} \right]$$

EQ(1) This approximate frequency values reduces initial trial and error time required and also reduce the number of iterations in Holzer method. Holzer method is trial and error method and very effective in finding the natural frequencies of multi rotor system. The basis of this method is that free vibration can occur with no external torques acting on the system. The residual torque value at the end mass is =156760.7314 positive value hence initial guess frequency is less than natural frequency ($\omega < \omega_n$). hence we should take slightly higher value of ω and repeat the same procedure. Till the residual torque at end mass is equal to zero. after trial & error, $\omega = 1305.65591$ rad/s

Table 3: Holzer's table for $\omega = 1305.65591$ rad/s.

Trial Frequency		Inertia	Inertia torque	Deflection at position of mass	Inertia torque of mass	Total torque of mass	Shaft stiffness	Shaft twist
Ω		J	$J\omega^2$	θ	$J\omega^2\theta$	$\sum J\omega^2\theta$	K	$(\sum J\omega^2\theta)/K$
1209.56	Damper Hub	0.09	131673.1854	1	131673.185	131673.1854	6.545	0.019521599
	FGT	0.0025	3935.56520	0.980478401	3858.73668	135531.9221	2.338	0.051376771
	Cyl-1	0.039	58989.5870	0.92910163	54807.3215	190339.2436	1.203	0.13566589
	Cyl-2	0.38	57380.2481	0.79343574	45527.5396	235866.7832	1.203	0.168116025
	Cyl-3	0.038	57380.2481	0.625319715	35881.0004	271747.7836	1.356	0.174645105
	Cyl-4	0.038	57380.2484	0.45067461	25859.8209	297607.6046	1.40	0.212122313
	Cyl-5	0.038	57380.2481	0.238552297	13688.19	311295.7946	1.203	0.221878685
	Cyl-6	0.039	59867.4083	0.016673612	998.205962	312294.0005	2.463	0.117271499
	RGT	0.026	35434.71723	-0.10059789	-3564.65765	308729.3429	4.3	0.072234287
	Flywheel	0.611	879284.2716	-0.17283217	-151968.611	156760.7314	-	-

$F = \omega / 2\pi = 207.8015$ Hz. The speed corresponding to this frequency is given by $N = \frac{f \times 60}{2\pi} = 1982.7756$ rpm which lies in the operating speed range of the engine. Now consider the second approximate natural frequency as $\omega = 2689.90$ rad/sec for further iteration of the second mode frequency. The same procedure is repeated and the second mode frequency comes out as $F = 560.4922$ Hz. Fig.(6)&(7) shows the First mode & second mode shape respectively.

Fig.(6) First mode shape

Fig.(7) second mode shape

GEOMETRICAL DIMENSIONS AND CRITERIA FOR DAMPER DESIGN:

1. DAMPER DESIGN PROCEDURE:

Fig8. Resonance curve for various conditions for auxillary mass dampers (1) damper Free $C=0$ (2) Damper Locked $C=Infinity$ (3) Auxillary inertia mass coupled to shaft by damping

The first very step in the design procedure is to make a tentative assumption of the polar moment of inertia of the floating inertia member or seismic mass. If the damper is attached to the front end of the crankshaft with the main purpose of damping of torsional vibration in the engine, the damper size should be from 5 to 25 per cent of the total inertia in the engine part of the system, excluding the flywheel, depending on the severity of the critical to be damped. Usually it is advantageous to minimize the torque in a particular shaft section. This torque minimization is done as follows: For a series of frequencies plot the resonance curve of this torque, first without the floating damper mass and then with the damper mass locked to the damper hub. Plot the curves with all ordinates positive. The nature of such a plot is shown in abovefigure.8The point of intersection of the is two cases is called the fixed point. The plot is shown as if there were only one resonant frequency. Usually only one is of interest, and the curves are plotted in its vicinity. If the plot were extended, there would be a series of fixed points. If a damping constant is assigned to the viscous damper and the new resonance curve plotted, it will be similar to curve 3 in Fig.8 and will pass through the same fixed point. All of the resonance curves will pass through the fixed points, If there is no other damping in the system except that in the viscous damper, independent of the value assigned to the damping constant. Therefore the

torsional amplitude at the fixed point is the lowest that can be obtained for the assumed damper size. If this torsional amplitude at fixed point is too large, then it is necessary to increase the damper size to reduce amplitude; if unnecessarily the fixed point amplitude is small, then damper size can be decreased. After getting the satisfactory size of damper, then obtaining damping constant is necessary which will put the resonance curve through the fixed point with a zero slope. By assuming slightly lower value of ω^2 than its value at the fixed point, and compute the torsional amplitude at that value of ω^2 with the damping constant C entered as an algebraic unknown. Equating this amplitude to that at the fixed point, the unknown damping constant C can be calculated. Calculation Repeated the with a higher value of ω^2 higher than the fixed point value by the same increment. Then the mean of the two values of C is taken which will be as close to the optimum value for design of the damper will permit. The resonance curve can be constructed such as, construct complete curves over a wide range of frequencies but only over a short interval in the vicinity of the fixed point.[6]

2. Damper Dimension: While designing the damper by taking into account of a space availability at free end of engine suitable value of outer radius R_o , Inner radius R_i and the thickness L of inner mass The first approximation, The value of $J/L = (\text{Inner mass inertia} / \text{inner mass length})$

Fig 9. First approximation value of J_1''/L Related with D.

The values of ring dimensions are, $R_i/R_o = 0.65$ to 0.25 ,

3. Damper casing inertia: Damper casing should have smallest possible inertia, Casing ratio $\lambda = J_1''/J_1''$ $0.35 < \lambda < 0.8$ $J_1'' = \text{Housing Inertia}$, $J_2'' = \text{Ring inertia}$

4. Deciding the range of Moment of inertia of damper ring Seismic mass: The mass moment of inertia of damper inertia ring has to comply with the following design condition. For the design of damper the Seismic mass ratio is given by, *Seismic or Ring mass ratio* $\mu = J_1''/J_2''$ $0.4 < \mu < 1$ Where, $J_2 = \Sigma(J_{cyl.} \Theta_{cyl.}^2)$ =Equivalent engine inertia from Holzer table without damper (summation up to cylinder inertias only).

5. Heat generation: Heat generation due to shear between ring & housing is another important parameter in torsional vibration damper. Since high temperature of the damper can cause the failure of cover seals, bearing, fluid viscosity drop and then quickly rise as fluid gels and finally solidify and its color will change to blakish. The damper inertia ring will be “Locked” to the damper casing, which affect on reducing the frequency of the crankshaft system and amplitudes of vibration will be high. Damper casing temperature should not Exceed 100 Deg.C to avoid the damper failure. If this working temperature limit exceeded the damper may seize due to overheating at elevated temperature.[4]The damper working temperature also affect the reliability of damper.

6. Heat dissipation in Viscous damper: The heat dissipation in torsional vibration damper is depend on number of parameters such as,

- Rotational speed engine.
- Damper Size
- Damper design
- Surface area. (m^2)
- Coefficient of heat transfer.

-Temperature difference between Damper casing and surrounding.

For the safe operation of the damper, damper designs should have sufficient surface area if not then fins should be providing to increase effective area.

PROTOTYPE SAMPLE DETAILS:

Prototype sample of different clearances & silicone fluid viscosity are manufactured for test the performance of torsional vibration damper on engine.

1. Damper Prototype Samples:

The prototypes of torsional vibration damper are manufactured for testi are as per below table No.4

Table 4: Prototype damper details

Prototype	Damping (Nms/rad)
Prototype 1	65.4
Prototype 2	110
Prototype 3	77.10
Prototype 4	77.80

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION OF VISCOUS DAMPER:

1. THEORETICAL /SIMULATION RESULT :(UNDAMPED CASE):

The figure 10 shows the amplitude curves of torsional vibration angular displacement at the pulley end of engine crankshaft system without a viscous damper. The undamped torsional vibration analysis shows that the torsional vibration amplitude of major order of vibrations for 6 cylinder engine are above the specified limit .such very higher values of the torsional vibration amplitude will leads to generating noise ,wear of bearing and engine part, and failure of the crankshaft. The resonant amplitude for major vibration orders of the six cylinder engine is 3rd order & its harmonic I.e 6,9,12 & remaining orders are minor orders.

The below figure shows the graph of torsional vibration amplitude in degrees (0-peak) Versus Engine speed (rpm)

Fig 10. Torsional Amplitude curves of torsional angular displacement at pulley

EXPERIEMENTAL SETUP:

In this chapter, the experimental setup and test methodology used for testing of Viscous type Torsional Vibration damper is described in details:

Fig.(11) Schematic Diagram of Torsional Vibration Test

While conducting the Torsional vibration (TV) test on engine, the optical rotary encoder is mounted on the crank nose end of crankshaft shaft with the help of mounting locator see fig (11). The test is carried out to capture the real time torsional vibration response of the Engine crankshaft. During the test Speed Vs Time data is captured using rotary encoder and PC-based data acquisition system and these captured signals are further processed in FFT torsional vibration analyzer. The FFT vibration analyzer processes this Time domain signal and gives the response in frequency domain. The Duty cycle sweep from Low Idle speed to High idle speed and from high idle to low idle speed is carried out at Full load condition on engine with required speed increment.

EXPERIMENTAL TEST RESULT:

The torsional vibration measurement test is carried out at engine model to obtain the crank nose end amplitude. Below figures 12-17 give the torsional amplitude values for different proto samples of viscous damper tested on engine for major and minor vibration orders of six cylinder engines.

Fig12. 1.5th order amplitude (experimental)

Fig.13 3rd order amplitude (experimental)

Fig.14.4.5th order amplitude (experimental)

Fig.15. 6th order amplitude (experimental)

Fig.16. 7.5th order amplitude (experimental)

Fig.17 9th order amplitude (experimental)

The damper surface of the temperature is measure to ensure the maximum temperature rise during the real working condition and to ensure the temperature limits of torsional vibration damper.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION:

The Experimentation has been carried out with various torsional vibration damper prototypes to compare crank nose amplitudes with number of prototypes samples with varying silicone fluid viscosity, internal clearances & moment of inertia.

For the case six cylinder engine, the critical order is 3rd order & its harmonic & remaining orders are minor orders called as “rolling orders “ of engine and system rotates as rigid body. but in case of turbocharged engine non-resonant orders are more severe. Below table (5) show the Theoretical and experimental torsional vibration amplitudes are compared and the optimization of the viscous damper is done based on heat dissipation characteristics and attenuation of torsional vibration amplitude at cranknose within limit of 0-0.2 deg.(0-peak) for specified application.

Table (5): Experimental Vs Theoretical Torsional vibration amplitude

Prototype	Torsional vibration amplitudes (0-peak)in deg.					
	1.5 th	3rd	4.5th	6th	7.5th	9 th
Undamped	0.184	1.038	0.250	0.858	0.341	0.210
Sample 1	0.151	0.385	0.142	0.114	0.035	0.038
Sample 2	0.158	0.344	0.139	0.117	0.035	0.038
Sample 3	0.154	0.35	0.113	0.093	0.029	0.027
Sample 4	0.156	0.343	0.10	0.096	0.025	0.023

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